

Thin-layer chromatography of certain metal cations with nonionic surfactant mediated mobile phase systems : separation of co-existing chromium(VI), manganese(II) and iron(III)

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Chromatography of eighteen metal cations has been performed on silica gel layers with micellar mobile phases containing nonionic surfactants (Brij-35 and TX-100). The mobility of metal ions was examined under variable experimental conditions of surfactant concentration, mobile phase pH and silica gel layer impregnants (urea and thiourea). The TLC system comprising of aqueous solution of TX-100 ($10^{-4}M$, pH = 0.8) as mobile phase and 0.1 M thiourea impregnated silica gel layer as stationary phase was identified as the most suitable for the separation of coexisting Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} . The interference of several cationic, anionic and molecular impurities on separation of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} was also examined. The lower limit of detection of these metal cations was determined. The proposed method has been used for identification and separation of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} from synthetically prepared alloys.

Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) being simple and cost effective has been used by several workers¹⁻⁴ as an analytical tool for rapid analysis of heavy metal cations. TLC is probably the most versatile technique as it can be used for the selective separation of metal cations on micro as well as on macro scale. Most of the workers have used silica gel⁵⁻⁷, alumina⁸⁻¹⁰, cellulose and cellulose derivatives^{11,12}, chitin and chitosan^{13,14}, polyamide¹⁵, etc. as layer materials in combination with aqueous, mixed-organic and mixed aqueous-organic solvents as mobile phase.

Since the first report^{16,17} by Armstrong and coworkers, the use of aqueous micellar solutions as mobile phases (MMP) have been the focus of numerous separation studies¹⁸⁻²⁰ because of their distinct advantages such as unusual selectivity, enhanced detection sensitivity, low toxicity, safe handling and faster analysis. MMP have been shown to increased fluorescent quantum efficiencies, thereby lowering limit of detection²¹.

The unusual separation possibilities in micellar liquid chromatography raised as a result of combined effects of relative partitioning of solute between (a) micelles and water, (b) stationary phase and water and (c) stationary phase and micelles, which is distinctly different from conventional liquid chromatography where relative distribution of solute between a stationary phase and a liquid mobile phase is responsible for separation.

Heavy metals have received considerable attention of analysis in recent past because of their physiological and environmental importance^{22,23}. Metals such as Zn, Cd, Pb, Hg, Cr, Mn, Ni, Cu, Fe, etc. are toxic and harmful to human life if exceeds beyond the permissible limit. These metals are capable to form stable complexes with bioligands containing oxygen, nitrogen or sulphur atoms²⁴, in which the metal remains in the form of complex cation or anion, and also controls several redox processes in living organism. The tremendous increase in the use of heavy metals over the past few decades has inevitably resulted in an increased flux of metallic substances in aquatic life. Industrial waste constitutes the major source of various kinds of metal pollution in aqueous systems.

Mutual separation of coexisting chromium (${}_{24}Cr$), manganese (${}_{25}Mn$) and iron (${}_{26}Fe$) is very important as these elements belong to the first transition series of the periodic table and show similar chemical properties. The efficiency of micellar systems for the separations of cations²⁵ and anions²⁶ has been reported and reviewed by Okada²⁷. Surprisingly, very little work seems to have been performed on the use of micellar mobile phases in the TLC of inorganic species^{28,29}. It was therefore, decided to identify important micellar mobile phases enabling highly selective separation of metal cations. As a result, separation of coexisting Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} from their mixtures has been achieved on

silica layers impregnated with thiourea with the aid of non-ionic micellar mobile phase systems. The proposed TLC method is selective and rapid, as it requires only 10 min for complete analysis of a sample.

Results and discussion

Mobility on plain silica gel layers developed with various concentrations of surfactants :

To understand the effect of concentrations of nonionic (Brij-35 and TX-100) surfactants on the mobility of metal cations, chromatography was performed on plain silica gel layers (S_1) using different concentrations of surfactant mediated mobile phase systems (M_2 - M_7) as developers. The R_F values of metal cations obtained in pure water (i.e. zero surfactant concentration, M_1) and in aqueous solutions of Brij-35 and Triton X-100 at different concentration levels (M_2 - M_7) show the following mobility trends.

- (i) In pure water, metal cations such as Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} show high mobility. The mobility sequence was in the order of $\text{Cr}^{6+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} \approx \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$. Metal ions such as Ti^+ , Bi^{3+} , Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , Ti^{4+} and Cd^{2+} produce badly tailed spots ($R_L - R_T \geq 0.3$), whereas other cations (Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , VO^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Bi^{3+}) stay near the point of application.
- (ii) With aqueous surfactant solutions of Brij-35 (M_2 - M_4) and Triton X-100 (M_5 - M_7), metal ions such as Pb^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Al^{3+} , VO^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} and Zn^{2+} remain very close to the point of application at all concentration levels of surfactants whereas Cu^{2+} shows little mobility ($R_F = 0.13$) and metal ions such as Ti^{4+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ti^+ , Bi^{3+} , Ag^{2+} and Hg^{2+} produce tailed spots. Cr^{6+} goes with the mobile phase ($R_F = 0.96$) and Mn^{2+} shows little mobility ($R_F = 0.38$) irrespective of the concentration level of surfactants in the mobile phase.
- (iii) Aqueous solutions of Brij-35 (M_2 and M_4) and TX-100 (M_5 and M_7) were selected for further study because of relative effective separation possibilities of metal cations in these mobile phases.

Mobility of metal cations on impregnated silica gel layer :

The results obtained on impregnated silica layers with urea (S_2 - S_5) and thiourea (S_6 - S_8) at different concentrations using M_2 , M_4 , M_5 and M_7 as mobile phases, show following pattern.

- (i) At all concentrations of urea and thiourea, all the metal cations except UO_2^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{6+} ,

Cr^{3+} and Mn^{2+} produce tailed spots. Cu^{2+} also shows occasional tailing. UO_2^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Cr^{3+} remain at the point of application. Cr^{6+} ($R_F = 0.94$ - 0.98) moves with mobile phase and Mn^{2+} shows R_F in the range of 0.3 - 0.47 depending upon the nature of mobile phase.

- (ii) Silica gel plates impregnated with $1.5 M$ urea (S_5) and $1.0 M$ thiourea (S_8) get deformed after activation.
- (iii) Tailed spots were found in case of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ti^+ , Bi^{3+} , Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Ca^{2+} .
- (iv) Comparatively better results were obtained on silica gel plates impregnated with $0.1 M$ thiourea with M_5 as mobile phase and hence TLC system comprising of aqueous solution of TX-100 ($10^{-4} M$: M_5) as mobile phase and S_6 ($0.1 M$ thiourea impregnated silica gel) as stationary phase was selected for further study. This TLC system was found most useful for achieving effective separation of coexisting Cr^{6+} ($R_F = 0.98$), Mn^{2+} ($R_F = 0.47$) and Fe^{3+} ($R_F = 0.03$) from their mixture (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of impregnation on R_F value of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+}

Stationary phase	R_F value		
	Cr^{6+}	Mn^{2+}	Fe^{3+}
Plain silica gel	0.96	0.37	0.03
Impregnated silica gel plate			
0.1 M thiourea	0.98	0.47	0.03
0.5 M thiourea	0.95	0.30	0.02

The separation of coexisting chromium, manganese and iron is important, as these are constituents of several alloys. Manganese bronze is highly resistant to seawater. The results encapsulated in Tables 2 and 3 reveal that best separation is at lower pH of the sample (Table 2) and several cation, anion and molecular impurities present in the sample influence the separation by lowering the mobility of Mn^{2+} (Table 3). The results presented in Table 4 clearly indicate

Table 2. Mutual separation of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} on $0.1 M$ thiourea impregnated silica gel layers with aqueous solution ($10^{-4} M$) of TX-100

pH	R_F value		
	Cr^{6+}	Mn^{2+}	Fe^{3+}
0.8	0.92	0.43	0.02
1.8	0.94	0.26	0.0
2.05	0.95	0.27	0.0

Table 3. Effect of impurities on R_F values of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+}

Impurity	R_F value		
	Cr^{6+}	Mn^{2+}	Fe^{3+}
Methyleamine	0.89	0.25	0.03
Dimethyleamine	0.94	0.27	0.02
Trimethyleamine	0.98	0.17	0.01
<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	0.85	0.21	0.05
<i>l</i> -Tryptophane	0.96	0.18	0.0
<i>l</i> -Lucine	0.94	0.24	0.0
<i>l</i> -Arginine	0.95	0.16	0.0
<i>l</i> -Lycine	0.95	0.20	0.0
<i>dl</i> -Aspartic acid	0.93	0.35	0.0
Glutonic acid	0.93	0.24	0.0
KBr	0.91	0.22	0.0
KIO ₃	0.88	0.25	0.04
NaASO ₄	0.94	0.20	0.0
NH ₄ SCN	0.95	0.22	0.0
NaH ₂ PO ₄	0.95	0.20	0.0
<i>p</i> -Aminophenol	0.9	0.28	0.05
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	0.8	0.23	0.0
2-Nitrophenol	0.92	0.19	0.0
3-Nitrophenol	0.92	0.23	0.0

that method is useful for identification and separation of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} from synthetically prepared alloys. The detection limits in μg , given in parentheses for Cr^{6+} (0.001), Mn^{2+} (0.1) and Fe^{3+} (0.05) enable highly sensitive detection of these heavy metals at trace levels.

Table 4. Separation of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} from ferromanganese alloy

pH	R_F value		
	Cr^{6+}	Mn^{2+}	Fe^{3+}
0.84	0.95	0.48	0.02
1.6	0.97	0.28	0.0
2.15	0.98	0.28	0.0

Experimental

Apparatus :

A thin-layer chromatographic applicator (Toshniwal, India) was used for coating sorbent materials on 20×3 cm glass plates to obtain adsorbent layer of 0.25 mm thickness. The coated plates were developed in glass jars of 24×6 cm. A glass sprayer was used to spray chromogenic reagent on the plate to detect the spot.

Chemicals and reagents :

Silica gel G, urea, thiourea (Merck, India); potassium ferrocyanide, 1,10-phenanthroline (C.D.H., India); polyoxyethylene²³ dodecanol [Brij-35], *iso*-octyle phenoxy polyethoxy ethanol [Triton X-100] (Loba-Chemie, India); methanol and dimethyleglyoxime (Qualigens, India) were used. All reagents were of AnalaR reagents grade.

Metal ions studied :

Ti^{4+} , Cr^{3+} , Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Tl^{+} , Bi^{3+} , Ag^{+} , Hg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} and VO_2^{2+} .

Test solutions :

Chromatography was performed on standard aqueous solutions (1%) of nitrate, chloride, sulfate or chromate salts of the above-mentioned metal ions.

Detection :

For the detection of various metal ions the following reagents were used.

(a) Dithizone (0.5%) in CCl_4 for Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ag^{+} , Pb^{2+} , Tl^{+} , Bi^{3+} and Hg^{2+} .

(b) Aqueous potassium ferrocyanide (1%) for Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , VO_2^{2+} and Ti^{4+} .

(c) Aqueous aluminon (1%) for Al^{3+} .

(d) Cr^{6+} is self-detected in the form of yellowish colour.

(e) Sodium hydroxide (2.0 M) plus 30.0% H_2O_2 (1 : 1) for Mn^{2+} .

(f) Alizarin red S (1%) in methanol for Cr^{3+} .

Stationary phases :

(a) Plain silica gel G (S_1).

(b) Silica gel G impregnated with 0.1 M (S_2), 0.5 M (S_3), 1.0 M (S_4) and 1.5 M (S_5) aqueous urea solutions.

(c) Silica gel G impregnated with 0.1 M (S_6), 0.5 M (S_7) and 1.0 M (S_8) aqueous thiourea solutions.

Mobile phase :

The following solvent systems were used as mobile phase : distilled water (M_1), aqueous solutions of Brij-35 [10^{-5} M (M_2), 1.5×10^{-4} M (M_3) and 10^{-3} M (M_4)], and aqueous solutions of TX-100 [10^{-4} M (M_5), 3.2×10^{-3} M (M_6) and 10^{-2} M (M_7)].

Preparation of TLC plates :

(a) Preparation of plain silica gel G plates :

The plates were prepared by mixing silica gel G with double-distilled water in 1 : 3 (w/v) ratio with constant mechanical shaking until homogeneous slurry was obtained. The resultant slurry was applied on the glass plates with the help of an applicator to give a 0.25 mm thickness layer. The

plates were air-dried at room temperature and then activated at $100 \pm 05^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h in an electrically controlled oven. The activated plates were then stored in a closed chamber at room temperature until used.

(b) Preparation of impregnated silica gel plates :

Activated silica gel plates prepared as described in (a) were impregnated with aqueous solutions of urea and thio-urea at different concentration levels using ascending development technique. The solution ascent was fixed to 10 cm in all the cases. The plates were dried and activated as described in (a) and stored in a closed chamber at room temperature until used.

Preparation of spiked synthetic alloy :

Ferromanganese (Mn-80% and Fe-20%) was synthetically prepared by mixing 1% aqueous solutions of Fe^{3+} and Mn^{2+} in 2 : 8 ratios. Aliquots of above mentioned synthetic alloy sample was spiked with 1% aqueous salt solution of Cr^{6+} . About 10 μL of spiked alloy sample was separately applied on impregnated TLC plates and chromatography was performed.

Procedure :

About 10 μL of test solution was spotted on thin layer plates with the help of micropipette. The plates were developed in the chosen solvent systems by the ascending technique. The solvent ascent was fixed to 10 cm in all cases. After development was complete, the plates were withdrawn from glass jar and dried at room temperature followed by spraying with freshly prepared chromogenic reagents. The R_L (R_F of leading front) and R_T (R_F of trailing front) values for each spot were determined and R_F was calculated as

$$R_F = \frac{R_L + R_T}{2}$$

Separation :

For the separation, equal amounts of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} were mixed and few drops of dil. H_2SO_4 were added to avoid precipitation. Aliquot, 10 μL of the resultant mixture was loaded on the TLC plates. The plates were developed, the spots were detected and the R_F values of the separated metal ions were determined.

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on mutual separation of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} was investigated by adding required amounts of standard buffer solutions to the mixture of these three metal cations before subjecting to TLC process as described earlier.

Limit of detection (LOD) :

The limits of detection of Cr^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} were determined by spotting different amounts of these ions on impregnated TLC plates, developing the plates and detecting the spots using appropriate chromogenic reagents. The method was repeated with successive lowering the concentration of ions until no spots were detected. The minimum concentration of ions detectable on these plates was taken as the limit of detection.

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